

COMPLEX COMPOUNDS OF BIGUANIDE WITH BIVALENT METALS.
PART IX. AMPHOLYTIC INNER-METALLIC COPPER AND
NICKEL COMPLEXES WITH NAPHTHYLBIGUANIDE
o-SULPHONIC ACID AND PHENYLBIGUANIDE
p-SULPHONIC ACID, AND ITS SALTS

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Naphthylbiguanide *o*-sulphonic acid has been prepared from α -naphthylamine *o*-sulphonic acid and dicyandiamide. Ampholytic inner-complexes of α -naphthylbiguanide *o*-sulphonic acid with copper and nickel have been prepared and their properties studied. These have been described as belonging to the class of inner-metallic complexes of the fourth order. They are all insoluble like the inner complexes of the first order. From these ampholytic complexes the corresponding soluble alkali-metal salts have been prepared and studied. The biguanide metal complexes behave as anions in these salts. Similar alkali salts have been prepared also of ampholytic copper and nickel complexes of phenylbiguanide *p*-sulphonic acid along with their corresponding cobaltic *tris*biguanide salts. A green modification of copper phenylbiguanide *p*-sulphonic acid has been obtained in addition to the red form previously described by Rây and Siddhanta. The two forms are represented as *cis-trans* isomers. Both give the same magnetic moment value of 1.85 Bohr, expected for a planar penetration complex of copper.

In previous parts of this series of investigation Rây and his co-workers have shown that biguanide and its derivatives combine with bi- and trivalent metallic elements like Cu, Ni, Pd, Co and Cr to form inner-metallic complexes of a new type, as these are not necessarily insoluble and non-electrolyte like the well-known inner complex salts formed by glycine, dimethylglyoxime, 8-oxyquinoline, etc. with metallic elements. The free amino groups in these compounds share the properties of a weak base and readily combine with acids and water to form salts and basic hydroxides respectively. To these the name inner-metallic complexes of the third order may be given. For, complexes in which the primary valencies of the central atom are completely satisfied by co-ordination with chelate groups and which become insoluble and non-electrolyte as mentioned above, are termed, according to Werner, inner-metallic complexes of the first order; while those in which the primary valencies of the central atom are not fully saturated by the co-ordinating chelate groups and which can therefore behave as an electrolyte, were named inner-metallic complexes of the second order by Werner. Examples of this latter type are furnished by acetylacetonates of silicon, boron, cobalt (ous), etc., as shown hereafter.

Rây and Siddhanta (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1943, 20, 250) have, however, prepared biguanide complexes which are completely insoluble and non-electrolyte like the inner-metallic complexes of the first order. Phenylbiguanide *p*-sulphonic acid combines with nickel, copper and cobalt to form such compounds. The basic character of the free amino group in these complexes is more than completely neutralised by the sulphonic acid group within the same molecule. The complex therefore like the co-ordinating molecule, phenylbiguanide *p*-sulphonic acid itself, behaves as an amphoteric electrolyte or zwitter ion. In order to distinguish these complexes from those of the inner complexes of the first order, we may call them inner-metallic complexes of the fourth order.

α -Naphthylbiguanide *o*-sulphonic acid, a higher homologue of phenylbiguanide *p*-sulphonic acid, has been prepared and a study of its complex copper and nickel compounds included here.

This reagent, like its analogue phenylbiguanide *p*-sulphonic acid, exists in the form of zwitter ion (II) as represented below :

(A_s = strong acid, B_s = strong base, A_w = weak acid, N = neutral). The substance is, therefore, expected to be practically insoluble in water, due to internal salt formation which has actually been found to be the case. It is, however, soluble in both acids and alkalis.

The complex copper and nickel compounds of naphthylbiguanide *o*-sulphonic acid like the corresponding complexes of phenylbiguanide *p*-sulphonic acid are quite insoluble in water resembling the inner complexes of the first order and behaving as ampholytes. They are soluble in alkalis. It is thus found that co-ordination with copper and nickel enhances the acid character of the ampholyte. This has made possible the preparation of the alkali salts of the ampholytic complexes. Acids, on the other hand, lead to the decomposition of these complexes. The phenylbiguanide *p*-sulphonic acid complexes also behave in the same way. A quite stable, bright red cobaltous complex of phenylbiguanide *p*-sulphonic acid, resembling vermillion, has also been prepared. The alkali salts of phenylbiguanide *p*-sulphonic acid complexes are comparatively more soluble and stable than the salts of the corresponding naphthyl complexes. From these alkali salts compounds of the composition, [Co (BigH)₃]₂ [Ni (PhBig. SO₃)₂]₃ and the corresponding compound of copper in place of nickel have been obtained. BigH represents a biguanide molecule. These salts of the metalbiguanide ampholytic complexes, with the latter forming an anion, belong, therefore, like the normal biguanide complexes to the class of inner-metallic complexes of the third order.

The inner-metallic complexes can thus be classified into four different groups.

The inner-metallic complexes of the first order comprise all those which are insoluble non-electrolyte with no free salt-forming radicals in the molecule, e.g., nickel dimethylglyoxime, copper glycine, cobaltic acetylacetonate, etc.

Those of the second order are represented by complexes in which the primary valency of the central atom is either incompletely satisfied or more than satisfied by the co-ordinating groups. These can, therefore, behave as electrolytes, e.g., silicon acetylacetonate chloride, sodium cobaltous *tris*-acetylacetonate, etc.

Inner complexes of the third order contain a free salt-forming group or radical in the co-ordinated molecules. This makes them behave as electrolytes, e.g., metalbiguanide salts.

Those of the fourth order are represented by ampholytic complexes, which are insoluble in water but dissolve in alkalis giving rise to the formation of inner complexes of the third order, e.g., inner-metallic complexes with phenyl or naphthylbiguanide sulphonic acid.

These are illustrated by the following configurations.

1. Inner-metallic complex of the first order :

2. Inner-metallic complex of the second order :

Silicon acetylacetonate chloride.

Sodium cobaltous acetylacetonate.

3. Inner-metallic complex of the third order :

Copper biguanide sulphate.

Sodium copper phenylbiguanide *p*-sulphonate.

4. Inner-metallic complex of the fourth order :

Copper phenylbiguanide *p*-sulphonic acid.

A green modification of the copper phenylbiguanide *p*-sulphonic acid has been obtained in addition to the reddish violet variety previously described by Ray and Siddhanta (*loc. cit.*). The nature of the product *vis a vis* that of its red modification is not quite clear. The possibility of cis-trans isomerism might be suggested, though instances of such isomerism in the case of copper are rather rare (cf. Ray and Chakrabarty, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1941, 21 609). The red modification changes to the green form slowly in presence of strong ammonia but rapidly on heating; a long time is, however, necessary for a complete conversion. This difference in colour may also arise from a difference in particle size or polymerization. A third possible explanation might be based on the assumption that the green form represents not an inner-metallic complex as described above, but only an associated complex of the type shown below:

or,

This resembles the copper salt of sulphanic acid or copper ethylenediamine complexes, the latter configuration having the possibility of occurring in cis-trans isomeric forms. But in view of the strong bifunctional character of the biguanide group giving rise to the inner-metallic complexes, neither of these configurations would represent a stable state. The green variety, once formed, is, however, quite stable and is not affected even by boiling water. The two forms may, therefore, be regarded as cis-trans isomers of the planar copper complex, the less stable reddish violet modification representing the *cis* configuration.

Evidences in support of the planar configuration for copper complexes are derived not only from the classical methods of stereochemistry but also from a substantial mass of physical data, specially relating to the X-ray measurements of the crystalline salts. Thus the planar configuration has been found for the cupric derivatives of β -diketones (Cox and Webster, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1935, 731), for copper phthalocyanin complex (Robertson, *ibid.*, 1935, 615), for dipyrindine cupric chloride (Cox, Sharatt, Wardlaw and Webster, *ibid.*, 1936, 129).

Though the nickel phenylbiguanide has been found by Ray and Chakrabarty (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1941, 19 609) in three different modifications, the corresponding ampholytic complexes of phenylbiguanide and naphthylbiguanide sulphonic acids have, however, been obtained only in one form. On the other hand, the sodium salt of nickel naphthylbiguanide *o*-sulphonic acid has been obtained in two modifications, red (stable at low temperature) and yellow. They might as well be related to each other as cis-trans isomers, the yellow stable form representing the *trans* variety. It might as

well be due to polymorphism as already referred to. Occurrence of cis-trans isomerism in the case of planar nickel complexes has been proved by several workers (cf. Sugden, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1932, 246; Cox, Wardlaw, *et al.*, *ibid.*, 1935, 459, 1473).

The cobaltous phenylbiguanide *p*-sulphonic acid, described here, differs, however, considerably in its physical and chemical properties from the similar cobaltous complexes with simple biguanide and ethylenedibiguanide previously described by Rây and Ghosh (this *Journal*, 1943, 21, 292, 323). Whereas the latter compounds are true inner-metallic complexes of the third order, as their colour and magnetic moment suggest (2.66 Bohr), the cobaltous phenylbiguanide *p*-sulphonic acid, on the other hand, is highly red and gives a moment value (5 Bohr) equal to that for a simple cobaltous ion. Besides, while the yellow cobaltous biguanide complexes are rather unstable and are readily oxidized to the cobaltic state in the presence of moist air, the red cobaltous phenylbiguanide *p*-sulphonic acid is quite stable in air and water. Only by the action of alkali solution it changes its colour to yellow with rapid oxidation to the complex cobaltic state, forming the alkali salt of cobaltic phenylbiguanide *p*-sulphonic acid. From these considerations it may be concluded that the red stable cobaltous phenylbiguanide *p*-sulphonic acid is probably an associated complex of the type discussed above in connection with the green copper complex and that, in presence of alkali, it changes to the yellow inner-metallic complex of the fourth order, which could not, however, be isolated on account of its great instability.

EXPERIMENTAL

Naphthylbiguanide o-Sulphonic Acid.—A mixture of sodium α -naphthylamine *o*-sulphonic acid (6 g.), dicyandiamide (2 g.), 70% HCl (7.2 c.c.) and water (60 c.c.) was heated for about an hour and a half with a reflux condenser, when white crystals of the substance separated gradually. These were collected and filtered. The product was purified by dissolving it in hot dilute hydrochloric acid and then reprecipitating by the addition of dilute ammonia. This was washed with water and dried in air. (Found: N, 22.88. $\text{HO}_3\text{S.C}_{10}\text{H}_8\text{.C}_2\text{N}_2\text{H}_8$ requires N, 22.87 per cent).

The substance forms a white fine powder, insoluble in water. It dissolves both in mineral acids and caustic alkalis, and is also sparingly soluble in ammonia.

Copper Naphthylbiguanide o-Sulphonic Acid.—Naphthylbiguanide *o*-sulphonic acid (2 g.) was dissolved in dilute HCl. A solution of $\text{CuSO}_4\cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ was then slowly added to it. The mixture was afterwards treated with dilute ammonia with constant stirring, when a blue-violet precipitate gradually separated out. This was purified by dissolving it in dilute HCl and then reprecipitating with dilute ammonia. The product was washed first with water, then with alcohol and finally dried in air. { Found: N, 20.82; Cu, 9.45. $(\text{HO}_3\text{S.Nap.Big})_2\text{Cu}$ requires N, 20.78; Cu, 9.42 per cent } where $\text{HO}_3\text{S.Nap.BigH}$ = a molecule of naphthylbiguanide sulphonic acid.

The substance forms a blue-violet powder, insoluble in water and dilute ammonia. It dissolves in caustic alkalis with formation of a permanganate-red colour and is decomposed by mineral acids.

2. *Potassium Copper Naphthylbiguanide o-Sulphonate*.—Copper naphthylbiguanide *o*-sulphonic acid (3 g.) was dissolved in a moderately cold solution of KOH. On concentrating and cooling the solution violet crystals separated from it. These were filtered and washed with absolute alcohol. The substance was recrystallised by dissolving in the least quantity of warm water containing a little dilute KOH solution and then cooling the mixture in ice. The crystals were filtered, washed several times with alcohol and finally dried in air. { Found: N, 16.98; Cu, 7.73; K, 9.61. $K_2[Cu(SO_3.NapBig)_2].4H_2O$ requires N, 17.04; Cu, 7.74; K, 9.50 per cent }.

The substance partially hydrolyses in water with formation of the insoluble copper complex.

3. *Sodium Copper Naphthylbiguanide o-Sulphonate*.—A moderately concentrated solution of sodium hydroxide was added to moist copper naphthylbiguanide *o*-sulphonic acid, drop by drop, till the latter dissolved. The solution was concentrated on the water-bath and then cooled in ice, when blue-violet crystals of the substance separated from the solution. These were filtered and washed with 70% alcohol containing a little NaOH and finally with absolute alcohol. The product was purified by recrystallisation as described in the previous case. { Found: N, 17.38; Cu, 7.90; Na, 5.65. $Na_2[Cu(SO_3.NapBig)_2].5H_2O$ requires N, 17.33; Cu, 7.87; Na, 5.69 per cent }.

It resembles the potassium salt in properties.

4. *Nickel Naphthylbiguanide o-Sulphonate*.—Naphthylbiguanide *o*-sulphonic acid (3 g.) was dissolved in dilute HCl. To this a solution of $NiSO_4.6H_2O$ (1 g.) was added and the mixture was made alkaline by the addition of dilute ammonia. The resulting rose-coloured precipitate was filtered and washed with water. The product was purified by dissolving it in dilute HCl and then reprecipitating by adding an excess of dilute ammonia. The substance was washed and dried as usual. { Found: N, 18.47; Ni, 7.73. $Ni(HO_3S.NapBig)_2.5H_2O$ requires N, 18.45; Ni, 7.73 per cent }.

The substance is insoluble in water and dilute ammonia, but dissolves in caustic alkalis to a red solution. It is decomposed by mineral acids.

5. *Potassium Nickel Naphthylbiguanide o-Sulphonic Acid*.—Nickel naphthylbiguanide *o*-sulphonic acid was dissolved in a moderately concentrated KOH solution. This on concentration on the water-bath and subsequent cooling, gave beautiful yellow crystals of the potassium salt. The product was recrystallized from hot water containing a little KOH solution. The crystals were washed and dried as usual. { Found: N, 17.92; Ni, 7.47; K, 10.0. $K_2[Ni(SO_3.NapBig)_2].2H_2O$ requires N, 17.93; Ni, 7.51; K, 9.99 per cent }.

The substance is soluble in water with partial hydrolysis and is decomposed by mineral acids.

6. *Sodium Nickel Naphthylbiguanide o-Sulphonate (yellow)*.—This was prepared like the potassium salt by using NaOH in place of KOH. { Found: N, 16.56; Ni, 6.95; Na, 5.46. $Na_2[(O_3S.NapBig)_2Ni].7H_2O$ requires N, 16.57; Ni, 6.99; Na, 5.46 per cent }.

Its properties resemble those of the potassium salt. It forms beautiful yellow crystals.

7. *Sodium Naphthylbiguanide o-Sulphonate (red)*.—When nickel naphthylbiguanide was dissolved in cold dilute NaOH solution and the latter was allowed to crystallize in vacuum over H_2SO_4 , red coloured crystals of the salt separated from it. These were washed and dried as usual. {Found: N, 16.60; Ni, 6.92; Na, 5.46. $Na_2[Ni(O_3S.NapBig)_2] \cdot 7H_2O$ requires N, 16.57; Ni, 6.99; Na, 5.48 per cent}.

8. *Copper Phenylbiguanide p-Sulphonic Acid (green)*.—Phenylbiguanide *p*-sulphonic acid (3 g.) was dissolved in hot concentrated ammonia. This was then treated with a solution of $CuSO_4 \cdot 5H_2O$ (1 g.) with constant stirring, when beautiful green crystals of the compound gradually separated out. The product was purified by dissolving it in acid and then reprecipitating from the solution by the addition of hot ammonia. {Found: N, 23.56; Cu, 10.68. $Cu(HO_3S.PhBig)_2 \cdot 1.5H_2O$ requires N, 23.79; Cu, 10.73. per cent} where $PhBigH$ = a molecule of phenylbiguanide.

Rây and Siddhanta (*loc. cit.*) have described a red-violet variety of the compound. Both the red-violet and the green forms are mutually convertible. Both give almost the same magnetic moment value. They both dissolve in alkali to give the same red solution from which the red-violet form separates by neutralisation with acid in the cold. The red form changes to the green variety on warming with ammonia solution.

Magnetic Measurements.

	$t = 32^\circ$	
Green modification :	$\chi_g = 1.84 \times 10^{-6}$,	$\chi_M = 1109 \times 10^{-6}$,
	$\chi_A = 1384 \times 10^{-6}$,	$\mu_B = 1.84$.
Red-violet modification	$\chi_g = 1.90 \times 10^{-6}$,	$\chi_M = 1128 \times 10^{-6}$,
	$\chi_A = 1397 \times 10^{-6}$,	$\mu_B = 1.85$.

9. *Potassium Copper Phenylbiguanide p-Sulphonate*.—Copper phenylbiguanide *p*-sulphonic acid was dissolved in strong KOH solution. After concentration on the water-bath alcohol was added to the cooled mixture. The resulting rose-coloured precipitate was purified by dissolving it in the least amount of water and then reprecipitating with alcohol. The product was washed and dried as usual. {Found: N, 20.83; Cu, 9.60; K, 12.0. $K_2[Cu(O_3S.PhBig)_2] \cdot H_2O$ requires N, 20.92; Cu, 9.59; K, 11.82 per cent}.

10. *Sodium copper phenylbiguanide p-sulphonate* was prepared like the potassium salt from the copper phenylbiguanide *p*-sulphonic acid and caustic soda solution. {Found: N, 20.98; Cu, 9.54; Na, 6.97. $Na_2[Cu(O_3S.PhBig)_2] \cdot 2.5H_2O$ requires N, 21.06; Cu, 9.56; Na, 6.92 per cent}.

11. *Potassium nickel phenylbiguanide p-sulphonate* was prepared by dissolving nickel phenylbiguanide *p*-sulphonic acid in moderately concentrated solution of KOH. The solution, after concentration on the water-bath, was cooled in ice when beautiful yellow crystals of the compound separated out. These were recrystallized from warm water. The product was washed and dried as usual. {Found: N, 19.75; Ni, 8.26; K, 11.03. $K_2[Ni(O_3S.PhBig)_2] \cdot 3.5H_2O$ requires N, 19.75; Ni, 8.27; K, 10.90 per cent}.

12. *Sodium nickel phenylbiguanide p-sulphonate* was prepared in the same way as the previous compound using NaOH in place of KOH. It resembles the potassium salt in properties. {Found : N, 20.89 ; Ni, 8.75 ; Na, 6.90. $\text{Na}_2[\text{Ni}(\text{O}_3\text{S}.\text{PhBig})_2].3\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires N, 20.87 ; Ni, 8.75 ; Na, 6.85 per cent }.

13. *Cobaltous Phenylbiguanide p-Sulphonic Acid*.—A solution of $\text{CoCl}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (1 g.) was added to an ammoniacal solution of phenylbiguanide *p*-sulphonic acid (3.5 g.) with constant stirring when the compound separated out in beautiful red crystals. These were washed and dried as usual. {Found : N, 23.95 ; Co, 10.15. $\text{Co}(\text{HO}_3\text{S}.\text{PhBig})_2 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires N, 24.10 ; Co, 10.17 per cent }.

The substance resembles vermilion in colour and dissolves in aqueous alkali to form a yellow solution which rapidly turns red from oxidation. It is quite stable and strongly paramagnetic.

$$\chi_g = 15.0 \times 10^{-6}, \quad \chi_M = 9915 \times 10^{-6}, \quad \chi_A = 10235 \times 10^{-6}, \quad \mu_B = 4.97. \quad t = 27^\circ.$$

14. *Cobaltic tris-biguanidinium copper phenylbiguanide p-sulphonate* was obtained as a light rose precipitate by adding a solution of cobaltic *tris*-biguanide chloride to a concentrated solution of potassium copper phenylbiguanide *p*-sulphonate. The product was washed and dried as usual. {Found : N, 32.75 ; Cu, 7.46 ; Co, 4.66. $[\text{Co}(\text{BigH})_3]_2 [\text{Cu}(\text{O}_3\text{S}.\text{PhBig})_2]_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires N, 32.94 ; Cu, 7.48 ; Co, 4.63 per cent }.

15. *Cobaltic tris-biguanidinium nickel phenylbiguanide p-sulphonate* was obtained as an orange-coloured precipitate from cobaltic *tris*-biguanide chloride and potassium nickel phenylbiguanide sulphonate. {Found : N, 31.62 ; Ni, 6.61 ; Co, 4.45 ; $[\text{Co}(\text{BigH})_3]_2 [\text{Ni}(\text{O}_3\text{S}.\text{PhBig})_2]_2 \cdot 12.5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires N, 31.60 ; Ni, 6.67 ; Co, 4.46 per cent }.